

A brief guide for the gRNA_create webservice

The gRNA_create webservice provides a simple interface to generate discriminative gRNAs which account for target diversity. It is a wrapper around the gRNA_create package¹.

Positive Targets:

A *fasta* file with aligned target sequences*

Negative Targets (*optional*):

A *fasta* file with aligned negative target sequences*

gRNA Length:

The length of the gRNA spacer (variable region)

Scorer:

The type of scorer that determines whether the gRNA will be able to target positive/negative sequences

- TwoPenaltyScorer: Allows up to two gRNA-sequence mismatches
- AaCas12b: Follows the AaCas12b mismatch penalty matrix (with a maximum of two gRNA-sequence mismatches by using $\max(0.5, \text{penalty})$)

PAM End:

The end on which the PAM is located

Scoring Metric:

The metric to rank gRNA performance

- Sensitivity: Only measures the gRNAs' coverage against "Positive Targets"
- F-Score: Takes the weighted harmonic mean between sensitivity and precision to assess the gRNAs' discriminative abilities between the "Positive Targets" and "Negative Targets"

PAM (*optional*):

The PAM sequence (leave blank for none; all IUPAC nucleotide codes are valid)

Email (*optional*):

The email address to send the results to. If the results take less than one minute to generate, no notification will be sent².

*For now, the aligned sequences must have the same number of nucleotides.

References:

1. Ahmed, A. *gRNA_create v0.0.2*.
2. Ahmed, A. *TaskMessenger v1.0.2*. (Zenodo, 2021). doi:10.5281/zenodo.5781773.